

Critical Perspectives on Micropropagation and Acclimatization Techniques in *Aglaonema*

^{*1}Deepa Switha Vishnubhotla

*Assistant Professor, Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree
College for Women, Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

²R. Ramya Krithi

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

³Alekhya Anne

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

⁴Hema Charitha Samanuru

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

⁵Hannah Anishika Valentine

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana
Email-h15149559@gmail.com*

⁶Shouni Niveditha Tenali

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

⁷Mini Fernandez

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

⁸Shruti Joshi

*Department of Biotechnology, St Francis Degree College for Women,
Begumpet, Hyderabad – 500016, Telangana*

Abstract–*Aglaonema*, commonly called Chinese evergreen, is a much-valued ornamental plant that is prized for its beauty, adaptability in different environments, and characteristics of air purification. This paper presents a comprehensive review of its taxonomy, morphology diversity, requirements for cultivation, propagation techniques, and breeding strategies. It focuses on significant aspects of its taxonomy among the Araceae family and discusses morphological features that are valuable in cultivar production. Techniques for cultivation are discussed, with a focus on optimal environmental conditions and integrated pest control strategies. The problems encountered during cultivation are also addressed, and the procedures to be used in an attempt to minimize and overcome them. The different propagation strategies, such as conventional methods, micropropagation, and bioreactor-based systems, are analysed based on their efficiency for large-scale production. Breeding and hybridization innovations and endeavors to enhance ornamental traits are addressed, as well as limiting factors such as slow growth and sparse seed production. The economic value of *Aglaonema* is also acknowledged at the international ornamental plant market level. Finally, biotechnological prospects for genetic improvement and conservation, and avenues for future research are considered in the potential application to *Aglaonema* advancements.

Keywords–*Aglaonema*, Micropropagation, Acclimatization, Cultivars, Ornamental, Foliage

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Taxonomy of *Aglaonema* and Diversity of Species

The genus *Aglaonema* belongs to the Araceae family under the kingdom Plantae, subkingdom Tracheobionta, class Liliopsida and the Alismatales order (NCBI Taxonomy Browser). Plants belonging to *Aglaonema* are further classified into 21 species such as *Aglaonema brevispathum*, *A. cochinchinense*, *A. commutatum* and *A. cordifolium*. The classification is based on their origin, leaf appearance and morphology. However, identifying different species of *Aglaonema* on this basis proves to be challenging as some species are very close in their morphology and may have similar origins (Li et. al, 2022).

1.1.1. Morphology

Aglaonema plants are characterized by their broad, oval to lanceolate and often variegated leaves with smooth margins. They display a large range of variation in the shapes and colours of their leaves (Budiarni et al., 2024). The leaves exhibit variegation patterns in different shades of green, silver and cream, which is influenced by genetic and environmental variables. The distinctive colour markings of cultivars like 'Silver Queen', 'Pink Anyamanee' and 'Pattaya Beauty' enhance their ornamental appeal (Figures 1 and 2). Among various species the growth habits vary; while some have erect stems the others show creeping growth with an ability to root at nodes (Silalahi et. al., 2023). These plants generally bear cream-white flowers on spadix type of inflorescence (Opryshko et al., 2019, Bashaboina, P., Lakshminarayana, & Kumar, 2023, Sayed, ELLeithy, Ismail, & Heider, 2023).

Figure 1: Leaves of *Aglaonema commutatum* (left) and *Aglaonema* 'Silver Queen' (right). (Utekar et al., 2023; Væksthusene& Aarhus, 2021; Royal Horticultural Society, 2025)

Figure 2: *Aglaonema commutatum* leaf morphology (Li et al., 2023).

1.1.2. Natural Habitat, Cultural and Symbolic Significance

Throughout human culture, *aglaonema* and related decorative plants have served as a sign of wellbeing. Southeast Asian humid, densely shadowed tropical forests, such as southern China, northeastern India, New Guinea and Indonesia are home to the majority of *Aglaonema* species (Nandini et al., 2023; Dabasiya& Mehta, 2024). In Malaysia, they are called 'Sri Rezeki' which means fortune/light and blessings/wealth, due to their significance in Feng Shui. *Aglaonema* plants are also known as Poison Dart Plants because of the calcium oxalate crystals present on their leaves and plant sap which poses danger to both humans and animals by causing irritation to skin & eyes, leading to further complications.

1.1.3. Growth Conditions

Aglaonema species tend to thrive in rich, well-drained soils under filtered light conditions, which are typical of tropical rainforests. They require protection from cold temperatures and excessive sunlight, moist soil without excess water, making it ideal for growing them indoors (Nandini et. al., 2023). Loamy soil with slightly acidic pH (5.6-6.5) is optimal for their root development. The plants prefer indirect bright light and moderate watering. They adapt well to being pot-bound, but they have to be repotted every 12-15 months for optimal growth. Humidity should be maintained at 70% for overall health (VanZile, 2024).

II. MICROPROPAGATION OF AGLAONEMA

Micropropagation is defined as the process in which small portions of plants such as shoot tips, embryos, seeds, calluses are inoculated aseptically onto artificial nutrient medium to produce multiple new plants by maintaining optimal growth conditions such as temperature, pH, light, photoperiod and ideal nutrients to establish the perfect conditions for plant growth (Abdalla et al., 2022, Al Qassimi & Jung 2022). This method, also known as PTC, has been extensively employed to cultivate a range of plants over the last 60 years including orchids, ornamentals, fruit and forest tree species, gaining favourability over conventional propagation methods as it is much faster, and can be performed throughout the year, and results in production of disease and pest-free plants.

2.1. Explants

Explants were taken from healthy mother plants that were typically grown in greenhouses or nurseries. Mariani et al. (2011) infused *Aglaonema* var. *Cochin* plant with 30 μ L benzylamino purine (BAP) (30 mg/L) to induce axillary shoot development for explantation. Explants typically used for in vitro propagation of various *Aglaonema* varieties are nodal segments, axillary shoots, apical tips, and shoot tips obtained from healthy mother plants.

2.2. Surface Sterilization

Surface sterilization of plant material removes epiphytic microorganisms, and the risk of explant contamination is diminished. Surface sterilization procedures for *Aglaonema* explant sterilization differ in the concentration and numbers of the sterilizing agents applied and the length of treatment time, but the overall method of sterilization is the same. These protocols also differ based on various laboratories, reagent availability, explant type, and the *Aglaonema* variant that is used. The removed explants are placed in a laminar air flow (LAF) cabinet, cleaned for 30 to 2 hours under running tap water, and then sterilized using various sterilizing agents. Ethanol or isopropanol (70%), sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution (10%, 20% or 30%), mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) solution (0.1% or 0.3%), Tween-20 (1-3 drops per 100mL), and Bavistin (0.5%) are the most widely used sterilizing chemicals for in vitro propagation of *Aglaonema* explants. Sterilization is also promoted by incorporation of other chemical compounds that include antibiotics such as gentamicin, tetracycline and chloramphenicol, antracol (Mariani et al., 2011), bavistin (Gadhe and Kale, 2023), Moncut (Abass et al., 2016) and ascorbic acid (Kaviani, Sedaghatoor, Motlagh, & Rouhi, 2019), and other fungicides and bactericides. *Aglaonema* explants are immersed in a mixture of these reagents, and the explants are washed under sterile distilled water to prevent the harmful side effects of the sterilizing agents.

2.3. Tissue Culture

After the explants have been sterilized thoroughly under aseptic conditions, they can be used for the production of multiple *Aglaonema* plantlets via tissue culture technique.

2.4. Culture Conditions

Nearly all in vitro propagation techniques use Murashige and Skoog (MS) media of several strengths (full, half, and quarter strains). The solution is sterilized for 20 minutes at 121°C to disinfect it, and its pH is adjusted to between 5.7 and 5.8. PGRs of varying concentrations are usually supplemented in the media at different stages of cultivation for enhancing explant growth. The explants are developed in fluorescent illumination with 1500–3000 Lux at 25 \pm °C and a 16/8-hour dark/light cycle of solar exposure.

2.5. Culture Initiation/ Establishment

Aglaonema surface explants that have been sterilized and placed on a medium of MS that contains 20 or 30 g/L of sugar in addition to gelling agents such as agar, gelrite, and phytagel. Solid MS media, either with or without PGRs such as naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA), are used to cultivate the explants, indole-3-butyric acid (IBA), 6-benzyladenine (BA), 2-isopentyladenine (2-iP) or thidiazuron (TDZ) at different concentrations to induce shoot initiation. PGRs are supplemented to the medium either as a combination of 2 or more compounds. The branches' length and each explant's total amount of petals (cm) are measured after the explants have been cultured on initiation media for 4–12 weeks.

2.6. Multiplication/ Shooting

After completing the establishment stage, the propagules are moved to MS medium that has been enhanced with various mixtures of BA, TDZ, kinetin (Kin), NAA, 6-BAP, or indole-3-IAA at different concentrations to facilitate shoot elongation and proliferation. Media used for the multiplication stage are usually augmented with cytokinins, as these PGRs are known for their ability to enhance shooting. The shooting of explants is carried out for around 12-16 weeks, in which the explants are subcultured at least 4 times onto MS media of the same composition used for multiplication stage. The information collected at this point of tissue culture includes the number of branches per explant, The quantity of leaflet each shoot and the shoot's length (in cm) Purbaya et al., (2025) demonstrated that TDZ was more efficient than Kin and BAP in stimulation of shoot growth of *Aglaonema* 'Ruby' microshoot explants (Figure 3). A mix of TDZ of 2 mg/L and NAA of 0.5 mg/L outperformed other hormonal factors such as the quantity of shoots, leaflet per shoot, and roots per plantlet (Taj ALdeen& Abd El-Aal, 2021).

Figure 3: Microshoots of *Aglaonema* 'Ruby' 12 weeks after being cultured on MS media supplemented with different cytokinins at 10 μ M concentration. A. BAP. B. Kin. C. TDZ. Growth of microshoot is greater on media supplemented with TDZ (Purbaya et al., 2025)

2.7. Rooting

After obtaining the desired quantity of leaves per shoot and shoots per explant, the elongated shoots are transferred to rooting media, in which they are cultivated for four to twelve weeks. Rooting media is often supplemented with combinations of NAA, IBA, IAA, or BA at varying concentrations, and explants are observed for the quantity of

roots each plantlet produces and root length (cm). Typically, auxins are supplemented to rooting media due to their positive impact on the rooting of shoots.

2.8. Acclimatization

Rooted plantlets with the desired number and length of roots are selected for acclimatization. To get rid of extra media, the plantlets are often cleaned using sterile distilled water, followed by chemical or PGR treatment like myoinositol to aid with acclimatization. They are then transferred into pots containing potting mixtures composed of different ratios of substances like peatmoss, perlite, vermiculite, sphagnum peat, cocopeat, sand, soil, compost, rice husk charcoal, and a variety of plant fertilizers. Peatmoss, perlite, and sand are most commonly used in potting mixtures. Usually, the survival percentage of rooted plantlets is recorded to determine the efficiency of the potting mixture, but other growth parameters of the plants are also observed to check for the ideal growth of the plantlets. Nugrahani et al. (2023) observed that treatment of *Aglaonema* plants with soil + compost + rice husk charcoal resulted in the best growth performance by the plants. Sayed, ELLeithy, Ismail, & Heider, (2023) demonstrated that application of brassinolide (broad spectrum, non-toxic PGR) and chitosan (natural biopolymer) as spray foliar significantly increased plant growth such as, (area of leaf, plant height, diameter of stem, dry and fresh weights), with chitosan (250 ppm) being more effective than brassinolide (200 ppm) by also increasing chemical parameters (such as total chlorophylls, carotenoids, phenols, indole, nitrogen and potassium) in *Aglaonema* plants.

III. DIFFERENT MICROPROPAGATION TECHNIQUES

3.1. Micropropagation of Axillary shoot explants of *Aglaonema*

Aglaonema "Valentine" explants of axillary shoots had been cleaned with distilled water, treated using 70% ethanol for three minutes, and then submerged in a 0.1% (w/v) solution of HgCl₂ with two to three drops of Tween-20. After that, sterile distilled water was used to rinse them three more times. To produce axillary branches, the explants were put on MS medium with 3% (w/v) sucrose and 2.0 g/L of gelrite. Explants grown on MS medium combined with 1.0 mg/L NAA and 1.5 mg/L TDZ, as shown in Figure 4A had the highest shoot proliferation (5.0). Similarly, the medium that produced the maximum fresh weight (4.48 g) and each explant's shoot length (8.5 cm) was 0.5 mg/L NAA+1.5 mg/L TDZ, suggesting that it was ideal for the growth of axillary buds. The multiplication of shoots in *Aglaonema* 'Valentine' was thus shown to increase upon combining cytokinins with NAA as supplements for the media. Half-strength MS media supplied with all concentrations of NAA and IBA were shown to be more effective in rooting than full-strength MS Medium, even though both full-strength and half-strength MS media supplied with all concentrations of these nutrients achieved 100% rooted. Most roots were formed by explants grown in half-MS media plus 5 mg/L of IBA and NAA, respectively (7.4 and 7; Figure 4B) (El-Mahrouk et al., 2016).

Figure 4: Micropropagation of Axillary shoot explants of *Aglaonema* 'Valentine'. A. Multiplication of shoots on MS medium supplemented with 1.5 mg/L TDZ+1.0 mg/L NAA (bar = 2cm). B. Rooted *Aglaonema* plantlets. C. Acclimatized plantlets in greenhouse (El-Mahrouk et al., 2016).

Axillary shoot explants of *Aglaonema commutatum* were cleaned on the surface by treatment as Tween-20 (15 minutes), 0.5% Bavistin (4 minutes), 70% ethanol (15 seconds) and 0.1% HgCl₂ (1 minute), then thoroughly rinse with distilled clean water. Gadhe and Kale (2023) demonstrated best results for shoot initiation was acquired from the culture of explants on MS media which contained BA at 1.0 mg/L and NAA at 2.0 mg/L (Figure 5A). Figure 5B shows that explants treated with 4.0 mg/L of BA and 1.0 mg/L of NAA had optimal multiplication in growth. MS medium with IBA at 1.0 mg/L and NAA at 25 mg/L was shown to be the optimum rooting medium (Figure 5C). *A. commutatum* was successfully grown using these auxins and cytokinin combinations in the growth media.

Figure 5: In vitro propagation of *Aglaonema commutatum* using axillary shoot explants. A. Culture initiation on MS medium with 1.0 mg/L BA+2.0 mg/L NAA. B. Multiplication of shoots on MS medium with 4.0 mg/L BA+1.0 mg/L NAA. C. Rooting of shoots on MS medium with IBA at 1.0 mg/L and NAA at 25 mg/L.

1.0 mg/L IBA+25 mg/L NAA (Gadhe and Kale, 2023).

Mariani et al. (2011) employed TDZ at 1.5 mg/L mixed with MS medium for the micropropagation of *Aglaonema* var. *Cochin*. The mother plant was administered by hormonal injection containing BAP of 30 μ l at 30 mg/l to induce the development of axillary shoots, which were then selected as explants (Figure 6.1). The explants were sterilized by treatment with Antracol fungicide (30 minutes) followed by 70% ethanol (2 minutes), and then washed with Clorox (NaOCI) + 2 Tween-20 drops and finally rinsed with sterile distilled water. For shoot proliferation and multiplication, TDZ at 1.5 mg/L and BAP at 3 mg/L (to prevent the formation of callus) were included in MS Medium (Figures 6.2–6.4). The fifth subculture showed the highest rate of multiplication. Sphagnum moss was utilized for acclimatization, and roots were grown in MS medium with IBA at 3 mg/L (Figures 6.5 and 6.6).

Figure 6: Micropropagation of axillary shoot explants of *Aglaonema* var. *Cochin*. 1. *Aglaonema* plant after hormonal injection of 30 μ l of BAP (30 mg/L); Arrow indicates the axillary shoot chosen as the explant. 2. Shoot proliferation of MS medium supplemented with 1.5 ppm TDZ. 3. Shoot proliferation on MS medium supplemented with 1.5 ppm TDZ+ 3ppm BAP after 2 weeks. 4. Shoot proliferation after 4 weeks. 5. *Aglaonema* plantlets on MS medium with 3 ppm IBA. 6. Acclimatized *Aglaonema* plant after 2 months (Mariani et al., 2011).

3.2. Micropropagation of *Aglaonema* using Nodal Explants

In 2018, Barakat and Gaber propagated *A. commutatum* using a tissue culture approach, cultivating nodal segments on MS media that included 3 g/L gelrite and 30 g/L sucrose. To find the ideal concentration for the explant's optimal growth, the PGR concentrations utilized in the medium were adjusted. However, the combination of 1.0 mg/L of NAA and 4.0 mg/L of BA is determined as optimal for the explants multiplication (Figure 7C) the inclusion of the most successful results was obtained during the starting stage with NAA at 2.0 mg/L and BA at 1.0 mg/L (Figures 7A and 7B). After undergoing multiplication, at the roots phase, the neoformed shoots were divided and nurtured. The best rhizogenesis results were obtained using MS media that contained IBA at 0.5 mg/L and NAA at 0.25 mg/L (Figures 7D and 7E). Following that, the plantlets were forcefully acclimated both in vivo and ex vitro using peatmoss and perlite mixtures in varying ratios. The *A. commutatum* plantlets showed 100% mean survival percentage in all treatments (Figure 7F).

Figure 7: Micropropagation of *Aglaonema commutatum* using nodal explants. A and B. Culture initiation on MS medium containing 1.0 mg/L BA+2.0 mg/L NAA over duration of 60 days. C. Multiplication of shoots on MS medium with 4.0 mg/L BA+2.0 mg/L NAA over 60 days. D and E. Rooting of shoots on MS medium with 0.5 mg/L IBA+0.25 mg/L NAA over 60 days. F. Acclimatization of plantlets on 2:1 (v/v) peatmoss and perlite over 30 days. (Barakat and Gaber, 2018).

Sawardekar and Sherkar (2024) observed that surface sterilization of nodal explants of *Aglaonema* var. *Red valentine* with 0.2% carbendazim (systemic fungicide) and 200 mg/L plantomycin for 30 minutes, followed by treatment with 70% ethanol (1 minute), 10% sodium hypochlorite, and 0.3% mercuric chloride (15 minutes each) resulted in 88.67% aseptic cultures. For six days, the explants were grown on MS medium supplemented with 3.0 mg/L of BAP. The explants treated using BAP at 6 mg/L and Kinetin at 2 mg/L showed the largest proliferation ratio (1: 253), and bud sprouting peaked at 84%. Maximum rooting (95%) was achieved with medium with NAA at 0.5 mg/L and IBA at 2.0 mg/L added as supplements. It was discovered that coco peat was sufficient to effectively harden the plants in the greenhouses (Figure 8).

Figure 8: In vitro propagation of *Aglaonema* var. *Red valentine* using nodal explants. A. Culture initiation. B. Sprouting of axillary bud. C. Multiplication of shoots. D. Shooting stage with pigmentation. E. Rooting of shoots. (Sawardekar and Sherkar, 2024).

3.3. Micropropagation of *Aglaonema* using Shoot Tips

To find PGRs that improved *A. commutatum* shoot multiplication and the ideal concentrations to employ for therapy, Abass et al. (2016) carried out investigative research. The optimal multiplication treatment was found to be BA at 8.0 mg/L in combination with NAA at 0.5 mg/L, which produced the greatest quantity of shoots in each explant (6.70). Transferring shoots to MS media at an IAA of 1.0 mg/L (indoleacetic acid) has been observed to maximize the induction of root development and rooting quality. For acclimatization, equal volumes of perlite and peat moss yielded satisfactory results.

3.4. Tissue Culture by Inducing Callus Formation on *Aglaonema* 'Butterfly' Leaves

Ratri and Ratnawati (2024) chose young leaves from *Aglaonema* 'Butterfly' plants and following surface sterilization, the leaves were cut lengthwise to measure 1×2 cm, after that it is kept on the solid MS medium which has the sucrose of 20 g/L, 0.05% Plant Preservative Mixture (PPM), Agar at 7.0 g/L and activated carbon at 1.0 g/L, BAPs of different amounts, and 2, 4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid. Callus formation was quickest (4 days after inoculation) in MS medium with 2 ppm 2,4-D and 1.2 ppm BAP, which also provided superior results over other treatments as 50% of the explants formed callus, with average size of callus being 0.82 mm, with lowest rates of browning and higher percentage (87.5%) of live explants.

IV. TEMPORARY IMMERSION SYSTEM (TIS)

TISs are a kind of bioreactor that, by letting the explant come into irregular contact with the culture media, can be used to generate secondary metabolites and enhance the effectiveness of plants' morphology and physiology in vitro. This creates the ideal conditions for aeration of the culture. The multiplication rate and plant growth can be increased by using TIS, while also reducing the cost of tissue culturing (Mirzabe et al., 2022, Méndez-Hernández & Loyola-Vargas, 2024).

V. OBSERVATIONS AND INSIGHTS

On assessing the various protocols, experiments, and studies conducted on Chinese evergreen plants, it is noticed that axillary, apical, and nodal tissues, along with shoot tips, are highly preferred as explants for in vitro culturing, whereas leaves are opted for callus induction. Explants such as embryos, roots, seeds, and protoplasts are usually not preferred for propagating *Aglaonema* in vitro, due to the high rates of success achieved in cultures that were established using apical and axillary tissues (Singh, 2024).

MS medium is used in almost all the propagation protocols, owing to its versatility, balanced composition of nutrients, and also for its ability to be easily modified with the addition of desired PGRs and other chemical substances to enhance and improve the growth of a wide range of plants. Salama (2021) demonstrated that MS medium at half-strength was more favourable than at full-strength for the establishment of shoot tip explants of *Aglaonema* tipe Dud Anjamani plants. However, the greatest shoot in terms of length (3.0 cm) and number of leaves (4.4) was produced by MS medium half-strength, explants cultivated at full vigor MS medium produced the least quantity of leaves (2.6) and the smallest shoots (1.8 cm). Additionally, it was noted that a half-strength of MS medium supplemented with IBA at 2.0 mg/L produced 3.5 cm long shoots and 5.3 leaves, the highest results among combinations of various MS medium strengths and IBA concentrations.

MS medium of Half-strength was also identified as more efficient compared to full-MS medium concerning rooting of *Aglaonema*, and on combination with NAA at 5 mg/L or IBA added to MS medium composed of half of the salt concentration, the 7.4 and 7 roots, respectively, were obtained, which were the highest values out of all the rooting media containing varying combinations of the strengths of MS medium and concentrations of IBA (El-Mahrouk, Dewir, and Naidoo, 2016; El-Gedaway & Hussein 2022). As demonstrated by the increased percentage of rooting and the greater quantity of roots each plantlet has been found that lowering the salt concentrations in MS media has a significant impact on rooting. This is attributed to the inhibitory effect high salt concentrations have on root growth and auxins present in the media. Therefore, by reducing the amount of salt present in the culture media, root growth is promoted. This occurrence has also been confirmed in the micropropagation of plant species other than *Aglaonema* (Woldeyes et al., 2021). Therefore, the media used at each step of propagation should be carefully chosen since the concentration of the PGR added to the media and the MS medium's strength have a big impact on the explants' in vitro growth.

Before inoculation onto the specific culture medium, explants of *Aglaonema* have to undergo sterilization in order to prevent any contamination or disease of the plants while growing in the lab. Surface sterilization, a universal practice in plant tissue culture, however, only aids in the elimination of contaminating organisms present on the surface of the explant. Establishing and preserving *Aglaonema* aseptic cultures face a major hurdle in the form of endophytic contamination, which cannot be removed by ordinary surface sterilization procedures. Pathogens colonize and reside in the vascular tissue of the plants, which makes it highly cumbersome to establish and maintain axenic cultures (cultures free of all organisms, except the one to be cultured) of *Aglaonema* (Karthik et al., 2023). Sterilization and maintenance of aseptic conditions are crucial aspects of plant tissue culture, without which microbial contamination occurs, which may lead to potentially fatal diseases of the plants. To establish a successful

protocol for micropropagation, the sequence and duration of treatment of the explants with different sterilizing agents have to be planned properly and executed correctly to minimize (and eliminate) the possibility of contamination of the explant. Based on the sodium hypochlorite concentration (NaOCl) employed and the length of time the explants are submerged in it, Budiarni et al. (2024) tried to identify the optimal technique for sterilizing explants (leaves of *Aglaonema Pink Katrina*) (Figure 9). NaOCl is commonly used to achieve chemical sterilization of explants owing to its easy availability, low cost, and overall efficiency (Pais et al., 2016). It was observed that immersion of *Aglaonema Pink Katrina* leaves in 5% solution of NaOCl for 3 minutes resulted in the lowest contamination (6.7%), and was thus determined to be the best experiment (Figure 10A). Explants immersed in 5% NaOCl solution for 1 minute and for 3 minutes appeared to be fresh and green, and did not display any alterations in their colour (Figure 10B).

Figure 9: Sterilization of *Aglaonema Pink Katrina* leaves using different concentrations of sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl). A. Sterile explants showing no growth of contaminants. B. Explants showing bacterial and fungal contamination (highlighted by yellow circle). (Budiarni et al., 2024).

Figure 10: Graphical representation of effect of concentration and time of immersion in NaOCl used for sterilization of *Aglaonema Pink Katrina* leaves. So (a)- positive control; So (b)- negative control; A1- 3 minutes in 2.5% NaOCl and 1 minute in 5% NaOCl; A2- 3 minutes in 2.5% NaOCl and 1 minute in 10% NaOCl; A3- 3 minutes in 5% NaOCl and 1 minute in 10% NaOCl; A4- 3 minutes each in 2.5% NaOCl and in 10% NaOCl; A5- 3 minutes in 5% NaOCl; A6- 3 minutes in 10% NaOCl; A7- 1 minute in 2.5% NaOCl; A8- 1 minute in 5% NaOCl; A9- 1 minute in 10% NaOCl. A. Highest percentage (93.3%) of sterile explants obtained by A5 treatment (3 minute immersion of leaf explants in 5% NaOCl). B. Highest percentage (90%) of fresh, green explants obtained after being subjected to treatments A5 and A8. (Budiarni et al., 2024).

The establishment of the highest axenic culture was achieved by Karthik et al. (2023) by treating explants from nodal segments and shoot tips of *Aglaonema* with 0.2% Carbendazim + 0.2% Mancozeb (contact fungicide) + 200 ppm Plantomycin (antibiotic bactericide) + Tween-20 as pre-treatment for 2 hours. This pre-treatment of explants resulted in minimum microbial contamination coupled with higher survival of explants. The pre-treatment was followed by surface sterilization, where explants were sequentially treated with 200 ppm Cefotaxime (antibiotic) for 30 minutes, 30 minutes in 4% NaOCl solution, 15 minutes in 0.1% HgCl₂, and 1 minute in 80% ethanol. As surface sterilization represents one of the most essential procedures in the propagation of *Aglaonema* in vitro, proper pre-treatment and effective sterilizing agents must be employed to achieve the highest degree of asepsis in tissue cultures.

VI. BREEDING AND HYBRIDIZATION

Many *Aglaonema* species are essential tropical foliage cultivars because of their ability to withstand drought-like conditions with high humidity and low light levels. Hence, they are popularly used for interior designing plants. However, the traditional breeding methods have been limited as *Aglaonema* exhibits dichogamy, which means that the female and male flowers of the plants do not mature at the same time, a phenomenon assumed to be nature's way of encouraging outcrossing (Henny, 1988). Commercial propagation of *Aglaonema* through vegetative methods is primarily carried out using cuttings and by dividing the basal shoots plants. This method allows for the maintenance of specific traits, but it limits the genetic diversity. Cultivars that produce the most suckers are grown in greater quantities because there are more propagules available for division.

By the end of the 1990s, there were 36 cultivars, up from 10 in 1975. Furthermore, cultivar retirement and release have happened quickly, and nearly every new cultivar was created using conventional breeding methods. Years of breeding and selection at the University of Florida under R.J. Henny's program produced the cultivars of *Aglaonema* in the Bayseries. The cultivar "Golden Bay" features white stems and a very brilliant cream and green colour variegation. The stem of "Emerald Bay" is mottled with green and white (Figure 11). Twenty new cultivars created by Thai breeders were introduced by Sunshine Foliage World in Zolfo Springs, Florida. These cultivars, which include "Peacock," "Jubilee Petite," "White Lance," "White Rain," "Illumination," "Brilliant," "Green Lady," "Black Lance," "Stars," and "Patricia," contain green, pink, or white petioles along with varying leaf sizes, shapes, and

variegation patterns. Along with "Stars," two cultivars created by Indian breeders, "Emerald Star" and "Jewel of India," are extremely resistant to cold temperatures.

Nevertheless, new technologies in tissue culture have provided the potential for rapid, clean propagation, which may improve production efficiencies and plant uniformity (Plant Cell Technology, 2024). In addition, interspecific hybridization has become more mainstream, as breeders developed selections based on new foliage habit characteristics such as leaf variegation, petiole color, and cold-hardiness characteristics (Tropical Foliage Plant Development, 2024). Existing cultivars that have been developed through interspecific hybridization, includes: 'Valentine', a cultivar from Thailand, with its foliage characterized by randomly distributed pink and green blotched leaves; 'Stripes', a cultivar from Florida, with better post-shipping quality. Furthermore, a recent study on a genomic resource for chloroplasts was utilized to determine the phylogenetic relationship of *Aglaonema* species, which could guide better breeding selections based on phylogenetic relationships (Comparative Chloroplasts Genomics, 2024). All of these developments represent a move towards a more active, globally aware approach to *Aglaonema* breeding.

Figure 11: *Aglaonema* 'Emerald Bay' cultivar

VII. EFFICIENCY OF MICROPROPAGATION PROTOCOLS IN AGLAONEMA USING DIFFERENT PGRS AND METHODS

Table 1: Comparative efficiency of micropropagation protocols in *Aglaonema* using different PGRs and methods

Study (Year)	Explant Type	PGR Combination (mg/L)	Shoot Multiplication (per explant)	Shoot Length (cm) / Fresh Weight (g)	Rooting Efficiency (%) / No. Roots	Notes
El-Mahrouk et al. (2016)	Axillary shoots	TDZ 1.5 + NAA 1.0	5.0 shoots	8.5 cm / 4.48 g	100% rooting; 7.4 roots (Half-MS + IBA 5)	Half-strength MS superior for rooting
Gadhe & Kale (2023)	Axillary shoots	BA 1.0 + NAA 2.0 (initiation); BA 4.0 + NAA 1.0 (multiplication)	Optimal multiplication at 4.0 BA + 1.0 NAA	–	Best rooting: IBA 1.0 + NAA 25	High NAA concentration boosted rooting
Mariani et al. (2011)	Axillary shoots	TDZ 1.5 + BAP 3.0	Highest multiplication after 5 subcultures	–	Rooting in MS + IBA 3.0	Sphagnum moss for acclimatization
Barakat & Gaber (2018)	Nodal segments	BA 4.0 + NAA 1.0	High multiplication	–	IBA 0.5 + NAA 0.25 (best rooting)	100% survival in acclimatization
Sawardekar & Sherkar (2024)	Nodal explants	BAP 6.0 + Kinetin 2.0	1:253 proliferation ratio	–	95% rooting (NAA 0.5 + IBA 2.0)	Cocopeat effective for hardening
Abass et al. (2016)	Shoot tips	BA 8.0 + NAA 0.5	6.7 shoots	–	Best rooting: IAA 1.0	Perlite + peat moss good for acclimatization
Ratri & Ratnawati (2024)	Leaves (callus induction)	2,4-D 2.0 + BAP 1.2	Callus in 4 days (50% response)	–	–	Callus induction for secondary metabolites
Mirzabe et al. (2022)	TIS (bioreactor)	TDZ-based media	Multiplication rate up to 2–3× higher than semi-solid	Faster growth	Lower cost per plantlet	More aeration, reduced hyperhydricity

The comparative study of micropropagation protocols discussed in the body of research suggests that axillary shoots always produce the greatest number of plants in micropropagation protocols for *Aglaonema*, with *A. 'Valentine'* producing 5 plants, and both shoot tips and nodal segments also demonstrate good propagation potential given the right growth regulator combination (BA + NAA; or TDZ + NAA/BAP). On the other hand, rooting was more effective on half-strength MS media supplemented with IBA or NAA. Using lower nutrient, half-strength, MS media for rooting provided more suitable conditions for the development of roots. Finally, callus induction using leaves supplemented with 2,4-D + BAP, while not as effective for direct clonal propagation, has theoretical potential for use using secondary metabolites in extract production and possible use in genetics studies. However, using temporary immersion systems (TIS) can cause two to three times more multiples to be generated and provide better quality plantlets while reducing costs compared to semi-solid culture systems. In conclusion, the choice of explant type, PGR combinations used, and the culture system had a significant effect on the efficiency, time, and cost of micropropagation of *Aglaonema*. Clearly, it is critical to developing protocols that are directed to the species and cultivar requirements.

VIII. TIS VS THE TRADITIONAL METHOD

Table 2: Comparison of TIS vs Semi-solid Culture for Micropropagation

Metric	TIS (Temporary Immersion System)	Semi-solid Culture	Notes / Key Observation	Source
Multiplication rate	2–3× higher shoots per explant	Baseline shoots/explant	Faster growth and higher plant yield in TIS	Požoga et al., 2024
Cost per plantlet (multiplication phase)	USD 0.002	USD 0.004	TIS reduces labour and consumable costs	Požoga et al., 2024
Subculture duration & acclimatization	~4 weeks / 3–6 weeks acclimatization	~8 weeks / 3–8 weeks acclimatization	TIS shortens cycles and produces vigorous plants	Požoga et al., 2024

According to the data (Table 2), TIS yields higher multiplication rates, shorter subculture cycles, and lower costs per plantlet than semi-solid culture; therefore, it is a more economical method for large-scale commercial micropropagation of *Aglaonema*.

IX. CHALLENGES IN GROWING AGLAONEMA

Although they are suitable for growing indoors and as household plants, there are several challenges, including physiological, biological, and environmental challenges in growing *Aglaonema* plants.

9.1. Physiological Problem:

One of the major limitations in the production and overall growth of *Aglaonema* is the chilling injury caused when the plants are exposed to temperatures between 0-15°C (Optimum temperature of *Aglaonema* is between 18-29°C). Dark gray and greasy splotches appear primarily on mid to older/lower leaves, between the mid-vein and leaf margin on the upper surface. On continued exposure to cold, the leaves may become chlorotic and may even wilt off or collapse in the event of significant damage after 3–7 days (Figure 12). ‘Silver Queen’ is particularly sensitive to cold climate, showing almost 38-68% damaged leaves at temperatures between 7-12°C in 24 hours (Henny et. al., 2019; Salama, 2021).

Figure 12: *Aglaonema commutatum* ‘Silver Queen’ leaves exhibiting marginal water-soaking and chlorosis after exposure to chilling temperatures. A. Untreated leaf. B. Chilling at 10°C. C. Chilling at 5°C. (“Temper.

9.2. Biological Problem:

Diseases of *Aglaonema* can be caused by bacterial, fungal, nematodal or parasitic agents. Bacterial blights, leaf spots such as those caused by *Burkholderia gladioli*. (Allya AlifiaPurbaya et al., 2025), stem rots caused by *Erwinia chrysanthemi* (Figure 13), and *E. carotovora* (Henny et. al., 2019), and *Xanthomonas* leaf spot caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* (Henny et. al., 2019), and *X. axonopodisp. dieffenbachiae* are common bacterial infections. *Fusarium* stem rot caused by *Fusarium* spp. (Henny et. al., 2019, Zhang et al., 2022) (Figure 14), *Myrothecium* leaf spot caused by *Myrothecium roridum* (Chase, 1983) and Anthracnose disease caused by *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* are some of the fungal infections affecting *Aglaonema*. Insects like caterpillars, scale

insects, and mealybugs also affect the plants by boring holes in leaves and stunting plant growth. All these are detrimental to its ornamental foliage appearance (Henny et. al., 2019).

Figure 13: Foliar symptoms of bacterial blight and rot caused by *Erwinia chrysanthemi* on *Aglaonema crispum* leaves. A. Leaf margin with rot, and midrib displaying systemic infection. B. Leaf blade showing marginal necrosis. (Alvarez, 2019).

Figure 13: *Aglaonema modestum* manifesting symptoms of *Fusarium* stem root rot. A, B. Symptoms displayed by whole diseased plants. C-E. Potted plants with stem rot. F-I. Progression of stem rot disease. J, K. Internal symptoms caused by stem rot. (Zhang et al., 2022).

9.3. Environmental Factors

These consist of elements like watering, humidity, temperature, and light.

- **Light Requirements:** The significant contribution to the growth of *Aglaonema* plants is light, and different cultivars reportedly show varied responses to light conditions. Low light conditions may result in elongated stems and pale leaves due to insufficient production of chlorophyll, but conversely, exposure to direct sunlight can lead to photoinhibition and stress, affecting the overall plant vigour (Hui et. al., 2023).
- **Watering Practices:** While underwatering might result in wilting and leaf drop, overwatering can cause root rot. The plants should not be irrigated till the top inch of dirt appears dry. The potting media used must also allow aeration and must be rich in micronutrients such as copper (Henny et. al., 2019).
- **Temperature and Humidity Levels:** *Aglaonema* survives well in high humidity conditions characteristic of its natural tropical environments; hence, low humidity can cause leaf tip browning and slow growth rates. Keeping humidity levels higher than 50% supports maximum growth. For the ability to effectively regulate and control both temperature and humidity, a phytotron or greenhouse can be constructed.

X. ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

Aglaonema is also thought to act as a phytoremediator because of its air-cleaning capacity. Research on *Aglaonema* has indicated that it was able to decrease concentrations of Toluene, formaldehyde, and benzene are examples of persistent organic substances (VOCs) found in rooms. *Aglaonema* plants are also able to uptake gaseous pollutants released by consumer products such as incense sticks, mosquito coils, and naphthalene balls, which can cause various problems like allergy, asthma, and even cancer upon prolonged exposure to the above-mentioned pollutants. The plants also reveal resistance to pollutants from the mosquito coil, and they do not reveal any observable damage after being exposed to such different pollutants. Consideration of these features makes *Aglaonema* plants very useful as houseplants, by contributing to lowering the level of pollutants, though there is still a study being done on how it takes in the pollutants and its effectiveness (Ghate, 2016).

XI. LIMITATIONS

Although current micropropagation protocols for *Aglaonema* are great at producing uniform, disease-free plants, there are limitations that restrict wider adoption and commercial viability. The significant capital costs associated with tissue culture facilities, labor costs for technical staff, and the cost of media components make the mass propagation of disease-free *Aglaonema* plants prohibitive economically, particularly for smallholder growers. The use of more traditional semi-solid culture systems has made scalability prohibitively costly and unwieldy due to accounting for the amount of handling and culture space available. While tissue culture staff can produce healthy uniform *Aglaonema*, somaclonal variability during subsequent subculture is still a problem, and genotype and phenotype have the potential to respond and change the ornamental characteristics and bioactive properties of a genotype over time. From a research perspective, the opportunities to study and optimize bioreactor technology such as Temporary Immersion Systems (TIS) as a propagation technology to support low-cost mass propagation of *Aglaonema*, are vast. The specific design of the TIS bioreactor is a primer, and it needs to be investigated so that we can develop some concrete understanding of how to optimize metabolite production for *Aglaonema* through perturbation of TIS protocol parameters like immersion frequency and nutrient supply. Further, yet unknown to

researchers are the conditions required to ensure stable expression of glycosidase inhibitors alongside their growth. Although certain bioactive compounds can be easily extracted, no studies have described standard extraction and few, if any, have offered helpful preclinical models to demonstrate the viability of their proposed use. If researchers could systematically develop methodologies such as propagating metabolite-targeted organisms and designing clinical trials, those methodologies alone would contribute to the sustainable production of plants and bioactive compounds.

XII. CONCLUSION

Aglaonema, often referred to as Chinese evergreen, is a well-known ornamental foliage plant known for its visual attractiveness, ability to thrive in various environments, and properties that help purify the air. This review offers an in-depth examination of its classification, variations in morphology, need for cultivation, methods of propagation, strategies for breeding, and challenges faced during cultivation. Cultivation techniques are reviewed, concentrating on the best environmental conditions and integrated pest control methods. Various experimental studies and protocols indicate that successful micropropagation of various explants of the usage of MS medium augmented with aglaonema with suitable PGRs such as BA, NAA, TDZ, IBA, and IAA. Different sterilizing chemicals are used based on the type of explant and plant species chosen, and surface sterilization techniques are also essential for getting healthy, disease-free plants.

Micropropagation of Aglaonema using temporary immersion systems (TISs) has also been revealed to be optimal for enhancing the physiological and morphological properties of the plant, and increasing production of secondary metabolites, thus being ideal for mass production and for commercial purposes.

Innovations in breeding and hybridization efforts to improve ornamental qualities caused a large number of cultivars to be developed, displaying a beautiful range of colours, leaf shapes, sizes, and patterns of variegation, and also the development of cultivars resistant to cold temperatures and other stresses. Aglaonema production is highly dependent on low light conditions, proper watering, optimal temperatures, and humidity levels. Endophytic microorganisms pose a major obstacle in tissue culture of Aglaonema, but contamination can be controlled with appropriate pre-treatment and sterilization practices. Overcoming the challenges in cultivation allows for further research on the plants and their environmental and medical benefits. The global market for ornamental plants also recognizes the economic importance of Aglaonema, due to its air-purifying qualities and for its aesthetic values.

The creation of efficient methods for secondary metabolite extraction and bioactive chemicals from plant tissues, as well as strategies for the mass production of Aglaonema plants in vitro, should be the main goals of future studies. The role of Aglaonema as a producer of bioelectricity should also be studied, and efforts are to be made to achieve large-scale production of bioelectricity using Aglaonema plants. Investigative research on the anti-pollutant, phytoremediative, air-purifying, anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, anti-hyperglycemic, anti-microbial, and anti-allergic abilities of Aglaonema plants and their extracts should be orchestrated to understand the biochemistry involved in these processes, as well as to replicate these properties in laboratories to create synthetic or semi-synthetic products and/or drugs which will aid in the improvement of the environment and curing of diseases. The various methods for micropropagation of Aglaonema should also be improved and standardized to achieve the highest growth rates with the least contamination, while also being economically feasible. Thus, the scope of future research on Aglaonema is promising.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. M. Abass, H. A. El-Shamy, A. K. Dawh, and S. S. Sayed, "In vitro micropropagation of *Aglaonema commutatum* Schott," *Zagazig Journal of Agricultural Research*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 363–376, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.21608/zjar.2016.101518>
- [2] N. Abdalla, H. El-Ramady, M. K. Seliem, M. E. El-Mahrouk, N. Taha, Y. Bayoumi, and J. Dobránszki, "An academic and technical overview on plant micropropagation challenges," *Horticulturae*, vol. 8, no. 8, p. 677, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae8080677>
- [3] N. Al Qassimi and C. Jung, "Impact of air-purifying plants on the reduction of volatile organic compounds in the indoor hot desert climate," *Frontiers in Built Environment*, vol. 7, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2021.803516>
- [4] A. A. Purbaya, R. Prasetyo, S. Samiyarsih, and Sugiyono, "Thidiazuron improved *Aglaonema* 'Ruby' microshoot multiplication for mass production and microfloriculture development," *Jurnal Biodjati*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 184–200, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.15575/biodjati.v10i1.34401>
- [5] A. Alvarez, "Bacterial blight and rot—Chinese evergreen," *PlantDiseases.org*, 2019. <https://www.plantdiseases.org/bacterial-blight-and-rot-chinese-evergreen>
- [6] A. A. Barakat and M. K. Gaber, "Micropropagation and ex vitro acclimatization of *Aglaonema* plants," *Middle East Journal of Applied Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 1425–1436, 2018.
- [7] S. Bashaboina, P. P., Lakshminarayana, and P. Kumar, "Effect of root microbial inoculants and chitosan on growth of *Aglaonema* (*Aglaonema commutatum*) cuttings," *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 2103–2111, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijec/2023/v13i102871>
- [8] K. Budiarni, I. Hindaningrum, R. S. Muharromah, R. Kartiman, L. Novita, L. Hardiani, and Kubil, "The effect of concentration and immersion time disinfectant on sterilization *Aglaonema* hybrid (Pink Katrina) leaves," *Biota: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu-Ilmu Hayati*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 219–225, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.24002/biota.v9i2.7632>
- [9] A. R. Chase, "Influence of host plant and isolate source on *Myrothecium* leaf spot of foliage plants," *Plant Disease*, vol. 67, no. 6, pp. 668–671, 1983. https://www.apsnet.org/publications/plantdisease/backissues/Documents/1983Articles/PlantDisease67n06_668.PDF
- [10]
- [11] D. Dabasiya and S. Mehta, "International Journal of Scientific Research," *International Journal of Scientific Research*, vol. 13, no. 6,

- 2024.<https://doi.org/10.36106/ijrsr>
- [12] H. I. M. El-Gedawey and S. E. Hussein, "Micropropagation of *Aglaonema* 'Lady Valentine' by axillary shoots explants," *Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences, H. Botany*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 129–142, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.21608/eajbsh.2022.273593>
- [13] M. E. El-Mahrouk, Y. H. Dewir, and Y. Naidoo, "Micropropagation and genetic fidelity of the regenerants of *Aglaonema* 'Valentine' using randomly amplified polymorphic DNA," *HortScience*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 398–402, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.21273/hortsci.51.4.398>
- [14] S. Gadhe and A. Kale, "In vitro propagation of *Aglaonema* (*Aglaonema commutatum*)," *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. j574–j578, 2025. <https://www.jetir.org/view?paper=JETIR2306966>
- [15] S. Ghate, "Assessment of phytoremediating potential of *Aglaonema commutatum* Schott for indoor pollutants," *International Journal of Plant and Environment*, vol. 2, nos. 1–2, pp. 87–92, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.18811/ijpen.v2i1-2.6622>
- [16] L. Haryanto, "The competitive and comparative advantages of *Aglaonema* farming in Depok City, Indonesia," *Ornamental Horticulture*, vol. 30, no. 1, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2447536x.v30.e242657>
- [17] R. J. Henny, "Aglaonema breeding," *Aroideana*, Central Florida Research and Education Center – Apopka, 1988. <https://www.roid.org/gallery/gibernau/aroideana/0110204.pdf>
- [18] R. J. Henny, A. R. Chase, and L. S. Osborne, "Aglaonema production guide," *University of Florida, IFAS Extension*, 2019. <https://mrec.ifas.ufl.edu/foilage/folnotes/aglaonem.htm>
- [19] J. Hui, C. Wu, X. Li, L. Huang, Y. Jiang, and B. Zhang, "The effect of light availability on photosynthetic responses of four *Aglaonema commutatum* cultivars with contrasting leaf pigment," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 5, p. 3021, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13053021>
- [20] A. Islam, T. Kamal, M. Hosen, N. Sharmin, S. Hossain, and N. Islam, "Lethal efficacy of indoor ornamental plant *Aglaonema marantifolium* (Schott.) against three economically important stored product pests," *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2198–2201, 2019.
- [21] G. Karthik, K. R. Kumar, A. D. Rao, D. Raju, K. A. Kumari, and T. G. Sankar, "Optimization of in vitro culture establishment in *Aglaonema* sp. by employing shoot tips and nodal segments as explants," *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, pp. 52–58, 2023. Retrieved from The Pharma Innovation Journal website: <https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/2023/vol12issue9/PartA/12-9-82-445.pdf>
- [22] B. Kaviani, S. Sedaghatpour, M. R. S. Motlagh, and S. Rouhi, "Influence of plant growth regulators (BA, TDZ, 2-iP and NAA) on micropropagation of *Aglaonema widuri*," *Iranian Journal of Plant Physiology*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 2901–2909, 2019.
- [23] D. Li, Y. Pan, X. Wu, S. Zou, L. Wang, and G. Zhu, "Comparative chloroplast genomics, phylogenetic relationships and molecular markers development of *Aglaonema commutatum* and seven green cultivars of *Aglaonema*," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 11820, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s4159802462586y>
- [24] D.-M. Li, G.-F. Zhu, B. Yu, and D. Huang, "Comparative chloroplast genomes and phylogenetic relationships of *Aglaonema modestum* and five variegated cultivars of *Aglaonema*," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 17, no. 9, e0274067, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0274067>
- [25] J. Li, K. Wu, L. Li, G. Ma, L. Fang, and S. Zeng, "Transcriptomic analysis reveals biosynthesis genes and transcription factors related to leaf anthocyanin biosynthesis in *Aglaonema commutatum*," *BMC Genomics*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-022-09107-1>
- [26] T. S. Mariani, A. Fitriani, J. A. Teixeira, and T. F. Chia, "Micropropagation of *Aglaonema* using axillary shoot explants," *International Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 46–53, 2011. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/284898199_Micropropagation_of_Aglaonema_using_axillary_shoot_explants
- [27] H. A. Méndez-Hernández and V. M. Loyola-Vargas, "Plant micropropagation and temporary immersion systems," *Methods in Molecular Biology (Clifton, N.J.)*, vol. 2827, pp. 35–50, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-3954-2_3
- [28] A. H. Mirzabe, A. Hajiahmad, A. Fadavi, and S. Rafiee, "Temporary immersion systems (TISs): A comprehensive review," *Journal of Biotechnology*, vol. 357, pp. 56–83, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2022.08.003>
- [29] G. N. and M. Malakar, "Phytoremediation using ornamental plants," in *National Symposium on Ornamental and Edible Horticulture*, New Delhi: Studera Press, 2022.
- [30] C. Nandini, U. Fatmi, and G. Kumar, "Influence of different potting media on growth and quality of *Aglaonema* (*Aglaonema commutatum*) var. Red Lipstick under Prayagraj agro-climatic conditions," *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*, vol. 35, no. 19, pp. 223–228, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijpss/2023/v35i193547>
- [31] NCBI, "Taxonomy browser (*Aglaonema*)," *National Center for Biotechnology Information*, 2018. Retrieved from nih.gov website: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser/wwwtax.cgi?id=174181>
- [32] P. Nugrahani, S. Wiyatiningsih, D. I. Larissa, and Maryam, "The effect of planting media and foliar fertilizer on the acclimatization stage on the appearance of *Aglaonema* 'Lady Valentine'," *International Journal of Veterinary Science and Agriculture Research*, vol. 5, no. 5, 2023.
- [33] M. Opryshko, H. Tkachenko, L. Buyun, N. Kurhaluk, A. Górczyk, V. Tomin, and Z. Osadowski, "Evaluation of the antibacterial activity of ethanolic extracts obtained from *Aglaonema commutatum* Schott and its cultivars against *Citrobacter freundii*," *Agrobiodiversity for Improving Nutrition, Health and Life Quality*, vol. 3, 2019. Retrieved from <https://agrobiodiversity.uniag.sk/scientificpapers/article/view/281>
- [34] A. S. and U. Fatmi, "Performance of different *Aglaonema* (*Aglaonema commutatum*) varieties under Prayagraj agro-climatic conditions," *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 41–44, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijpss/2024/v36i84833>
- [35] G. M. Y. Salama, "Studies on micropropagation of *Aglaonema* type Dud Anjamani plants," *Middle East Journal of Agriculture Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 53–59, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.36632/mejar/2021.10.1.3>
- [36] S. Sawardekar and S. Sherkar, "Advances in micropropagation of *Aglaonema* var. Red Valentine," *International Journal of Advanced Biochemistry Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 668–675, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26174693.2024.v8.i2h.821>
- [37] A. S. Sayed, A. S. EL-Leithy, E. E. Ismail, and S. M. Heider, "Effect of brassinolide and chitosan on growth and chemical composition of *Aglaonema commutatum* plant," *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry (EJCHEM)*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 419–427, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejchem.2022.156931.6807>
- [38] T. P. Silalahi and P. Murni, "Effect of light intensity on phenology and morphological characteristics of *Aglaonema Bigroy* (*Aglaonema sp.*) leaves," *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 10892–10901, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jppipa.v9i12.5593>
- [39] A. Singh, "Which parts of the plant are best for tissue culture and how should they be sterilized," *Plant Cell Technology Blog*, Nov. 2024. <https://plantcelltechnology.com/blogs/blog/which-parts-of-the-plant-to-use-for-induction-and-how-to-sterilize-them>
- [40] A. M. Taj Aldeen and M. S. Abd El-Aal, "Enhancement of *Aglaonema commutatum* propagation using thiazuron and naphthalene acetic acid in vitro," *London Journal of Medical and Health Research*, vol. 21, no. 10, 2021.
- [41] "Temperature," *APSnet*, 2019. Retrieved from Temperature website: <https://www.apsnet.org/edcenter/apsnetfeatures/Pages/Temperature.aspx>
- [42] S. Utekar, R. Bhise, P. Ghorpade, S. Sawardekar, and S. Sherkar, "In vitro propagation of valuable ornamental *Aglaonema* species: A review," *Bioscience Discovery*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 40–52, 2023.
- [43] "*Aglaonema commutatum*," *Væksthusene & Aarhus C*, 2021. Retrieved from <https://powo.science.kew.org/taxon/urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:84050-1/images>
- [44] J. VanZile, "How to Grow & Care for Chinese evergreen (*Aglaonema*) Indoors," *The Spruce*, Aug. 5, 2024. <https://www.thespruce.com/grow-aglaonema-houseplants-1902734>
- [45] G. G. Woldeyes, T. F. Senbeta, A. Y. Aduana, and A. W. Abegaz, "The effect of MS strength, pH, and sucrose concentrations on in vitro propagation of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) from shoot tip explants," *Research Square*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-153475/v1>

- [46] Y. Zhang, C. Chen, Z. Mai, J. Lin, L. Nie, S. S. N. Maharachchikumbura, and I. S. Manawasinghe, "Co-infection of *Fusarium aglaonematis* sp. nov. and *Fusarium elaeidis* causing stem rot in *Aglaonema modestum* in China," *Front. Microbiol.*, vol. 13, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.930790>
- [47] "Aglaonema Tissue Culture: Here's What You Should Know," *Plant Cell Technology*, 2024. Retrieved from <https://plantcelltechnology.com/blogs/blog/aglaonema-tissue-culture-heres-what-you-should-know>
- [48] "Breeding Techniques for Aglaonema and Dieffenbachia," *Tropical Foliage Plant Development*, 2024. *University of Florida*.
- [49] "Comparative Chloroplast Genomics, Phylogenetic Relationships, and Genetic Diversity of Aglaonema," *PMC*, 2024. Retrieved from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11116548/>
- [50] M. S. Islam, M. S. Hossain, and M. M. Rahman, "Biological activities of Aglaonema plants: A review," *Asian Pac. J. Trop. Biomed.*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 397–404, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2221-1691.263167>
- [51] M. Opryshko, M. Gryshko, and V. Shcherbyna, "Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extracts of *Aglaonema commutatum* Schott and its cultivars against *Enterococcus faecalis* strains," *CABI Agric. Biosci.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–6, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43170-019-00017-5>